

THE POTENTIAL OF DIVING TECHNOLOGY ON THE COLLECTION OF MESOPHOTIC FISHES FOR ORNAMENTAL AQUACULTURE

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When diving at great depths, away from the coastal zone, there is a surprising variety of ecosystems not yet comprehensively explored by the aquarium trade. After 80 submersible diving sessions carried out near the Caribbean island of Curaçao, researchers recorded about 4,500 fishes from 71 species, with one-fifth of those being new species. It shows that marine fish biodiversity is still poorly understood. Considering the need for research and the potential of newly discovered species of marine fish, a Brazilian company decided to focus on this matter, developing technologies for collecting marine fishes from mesophotic depths (40-130 m).

Biomarine Aquicultura Ornamental is a marine ornamental fish farming company established in São Paulo, Brazil, in 2018. It works with reproduction of several species, especially clownfish, and has been developing new larviculture techniques focused on the production of new food organisms, promoting the diversification of captive breeding species. Company efforts have already resulted in the isolation and culture of the copepod *Bestiolina similis* (Sewell 1914) and *Pseudodiaptomus richardi* (Dahl 1894). These strains have been successfully used for feeding captive-bred ornamental fish species such as the mandarin fish *Syngniscus splendidus*, the sharknose goby *Elacatinus evelynae*, the orchid dottyback *Pseudochromis fridimani* and more recently, the sea goldie *Pseudanthias squamipinnis*.

All over the world, research centers and ornamental companies are joining efforts to reproduce reef fishes in captivity. In this sense, in 2015, the Oceanic Institute of Hawaii (Pacific University) first demonstrated successful techniques for the captive breeding of the yellow tang *Zebrasoma flavescens* (Callan 2018). In 2017, researchers from the Tropical Aquaculture Laboratory, University of Florida described captive reproduction of *Paracanthurus hepatus* (DiMaggio 2017). Likewise, Biomarine is fully interested in investing in new saltwater fish species, as the company believes that reef fish

Hyperbaric chamber used by Biomarine (top). Power handle detail (bottom).

aquaculture might contribute to the conservation of marine environments.

In 2022, Biomarine, along with the Marine Fish Laboratory (Fisheries Institute), demonstrated the captive breeding of *Pseudanthias squamipinnis* (Sanches *et al.* 2022). These studies provided evidence that technology can currently assist reproduction of many marine ornamental fish species in captivity. Therefore, technological development has been undertaken to promote scale gains by reducing costs and expanding the supply of these organisms to the aquarium trade. Such studies, however, are usually focused on fish species from coral reefs in the altyphotic zone (between 0 and 40 m deep).

There are few studies approaching the mesophotic

fishes, comprising species that inhabit the mesophotic zone between 40 and 150 m deep (Pyle 2019). The term mesophotic designates a region of low luminosity. In other words, at these sites, there is a progressive increase in ocean depth and, consequently, a proportional reduction in sunlight. There is a correlation between depth and changes in the profile of species that detect by the visual sense (Rocha 2018). In those areas, mesophotic reefs provide shelter for many species that are not found in the altyphotic reef habitat. Furthermore, scientists believe that mesophotic reefs play an important role in protecting the fauna of altyphotic reefs as the deep waters around these zones may also function as a refuge for species in the case of mass mortality in the altyphotic zone, enabling the regeneration of the fauna associated with coral reefs.

Altyphotic reef species are readily available for research because they are relatively easy to capture, considering that they inhabit depths accessible to fishing community members and conventional scuba divers, and are also widely available in saltwater fish markets. In addition, these species have been incessantly targeted for the aquarium fish hobby trade, so there is already knowledge and interest in these species. The biodiversity of altyphotic reefs is subjected to intense

Detail of the hyperbaric chamber used by Biomarine.

Detail of the control valve of the hyperbaric chamber used by Biomarine.

collection pressures, which also justifies making the effort on captive reproduction. In contrast, mesophotic species are rarely marketed, and when available, are very expensive. Thus, live individuals from mesophotic regions are not always accessible for scientific experiments on reproduction in captivity.

Although it is not possible to state mesophotic fishes are affected by the ornamental fish trade, it cannot be presumed that biodiversity of those ecosystems are totally preserved.

Recent studies indicate signs of degradation in mesophotic coral reef ecosystems, highlighting the urgent need for governments to take action to protect those environments (Rocha 2018). Climate change, habitat competition with invasive species, professional, sport or ghost fishing, pollution, ocean acidification, mining activities, oil extraction and even naval accidents are some of the factors that impact mesophotic fauna.

Mesophotic regions were still largely unknown (Pinheiro 2016), as they were located at a depth where scuba diving was not operationally viable and tended to be neglected even when manned submersibles were used. Considering the high operational cost of this equipment, its use tended to focus on greater depths, normally below 150 m, justifying the investment (Pyle 1996). As a result, the mesophotic depth range remained poorly known, although holding many species not yet described (Pyle 2000, Pinheiro 2016).

As Richard L. Pyle indicated in his 1996 article, “Exploring deep coral reefs: how much biodiversity are we losing?” the “Twilight Zone” or mesophotic regions have received little attention from researchers despite the available technology for exploration of abyssal and spatial zones. Pyle’s pioneering vision in the 1990s stimulated the scientific community to apply closed-circuit rebreather technology as a diving tool to assess mesophotic zones in subsequent years. Currently a large number of researchers are using this technical equipment to conduct studies in these areas.

Using a rebreather allows divers to submerge for long periods. It is also silent and produces no bubbles, which makes it easier to approach live organisms, allowing the collection of specimens with

ROV used by Biomarine (Qysea Fifish V6S, 200m cable).

basic manual equipment. On the other hand, it is a high-cost apparatus, requiring a backup system, rigorous training and careful maintenance (Mocsári 2015). Diving with helium-based gas mixtures, especially trimix (a mixture of oxygen, nitrogen and helium), has allowed this equipment to be used for diving in the mesophotic range. By defining an appropriate plan and the correct proportion of gases, the diver can control hyperoxia and the narcotic level of the mixture (Mocsári 2015).

Considering these challenges and opportunities, Biomarine has been working towards assimilation and technological development in the mesophotic marine fish area, with the purpose of collecting specimens for the development of reproductive protocols, resulting in the expansion of knowledge about these species. Development of capture techniques can allow mesophotic specimens to be available at different larval stages for ichthyological studies, also enabling the supply of young fish for scientific purposes.

Economically, the reproduction of mesophotic species shows great potential. In fact, mesophotic fish are rare in the aquarium market and, when available, reach high economic values. For example, specimens of French butterflyfish *Prognathodes guyanensis* from the Caribbean Sea, reach a retail value of US\$2,500 in the North American market.

Based on this challenge and opportunity, the Biomarine team planned and executed two mesophotic diving operations in Bahia, Brazil, aiming to evaluate the operational conditions of fish capture at depths below 100 m. Indeed, the collection of fish from mesophotic depths and to safely bring them to surface is a great challenge. Hence, operations were planned one year in advance. The time was used for construction and acquisition of equipment, methodological planning, system experimentation and adjustments. Divers László Mocsári and Peter Tofte accepted the invitation to participate, operating as deep-sea divers. Both are highly experienced technical divers accustomed to extreme rebreather diving and were responsible for each dive’s individual planning, including decompression stops, ‘bail out’ systems and gas mixtures.

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Fish capture was designed to be carried out with hand nets. In addition, divers were instructed to collect predetermined species that were selected for captive breeding studies: eyestripe bass *Liopropoma aberrans*, French butterflyfish *Prognathodes guyanensis* and rough-tongue bass *Pronotogrammus*

Location of dives on the coast of Bahia, Brazil.

martinicensis, all available at the planned depth. Species were chosen based on images from previous mesophotic dives made at the site.

To enable decompression of the collected fishes, the SubCAS technique (Shepherd 2018) was adopted with some modifications. It consists of a portable, submersible hyperbaric chamber that is taken to depth by divers. Captured fish are kept in the chamber under pressure to avoid occurrence of hyperbaric issues, allowing decompression process to occur at the surface in a slow and controlled way, avoiding rapid changes that can cause barotraumas and sometimes death.

The SubCAS technique keeps pressure stable inside the hyperbaric chamber during the course of ascending following completion of a dive with the aid of a small air bubble injected before the chamber's complete closing. This air bubble expands as divers head to the surface, compensating for the reduction in external pressure and compliance of the polycarbonate chamber body, thus preventing significant internal pressure variations (Boyle-Mariotte Law). For fish, the pressure does not change significantly even when the chamber is already at the surface. The chamber closure was planned to occur between 60 and 70 m to prevent fish from being exposed to excessive decompression from the collection point (Shepherd 2018).

Two methods were tested to assure chamber recovery: the first consisted of a manual search by the support team when the deep-sea divers reached 30 m depth, within one hour after the beginning of the dive, following the SubCAS standard operating method. The second method consisted of finding the divers with a small ROV (remotely operated underwater vehicle) at 70 m deep, 30 min after the start of the dive; then, the surface team quickly pulls the equipment and camera fixed to the diver's robotic arm. This second method was designed with an additional mechanism to reduce the chamber's exposure to high temperature at the water surface.

After being received at the surface, the chamber was connected to a high-pressure system that promotes saltwater recirculation, keeping water oxygenation for the captured specimens. Pressure is maintained using a high-pressure water pump¹ powered by two 55-A stationary batteries. The internal pressure was determined by operating a pressure relief valve.

In the hours that followed, while the divers' return was awaited, as divers need to carry out their long decompression process, the quality of the water for the fish was maintained by exchanging it for cooled surface seawater, removing nitrogenous compounds and maintaining the ideal physical and chemical conditions for captured fish. At this stage, temperature needs to be strictly controlled using ice in closed bags to keep parameters close to that found where fish were captured. For this, an electronic thermostat with DC power² was used, with a probe submerged in the recirculation water, whose purpose is to facilitate temperature evaluation, allowing quick adoption of corrective measures.

Upon returning to port, the chamber is sealed again at current working pressure and transported to a nearby base, where the set is reconnected to the pressure line. In this phase, the system is powered by AC energy and temperature is controlled using a well-sized chiller.

The hyperbaric chamber built by Biomarine underwent certain modifications compared to the original model of the SubCAS (Shepherd 2018). First, a strength handle constructed with 15-mm HDPE using a CNC milling machine was affixed to structural points with stainless steel screws. In the original project, this structure is composed of a PVC pipe spare with a register used to close the chamber, which is also used as a force lever that allows the application of the necessary torque to close and seal a lid next to the chamber's body. The Biomarine team considered the implementation of a true force loop to be more convenient as it eliminates the risk of PVC breakage and also serves as protection and cover for the inlet and outlet registers of the hyperbaric chamber, which were also modified to be minimalistic.

Two simple quick-connect valves were adopted to thread on the 1/4" type inlet and 3/8" type outlet connections of the hyperbaric chambers. These registers have their opening/closing handle shortened to prevent them from being accidentally opened during ascent. In addition, a conventional 3/8" pressure control valve for filtering systems was installed in the pressure line. It was a simple, low-cost and functional solution, because the valve originally used in the original design of the SubCAS³ is not easily found in the Brazilian market.

The hyperbaric system generates a back pressure that prevents fish from being brought to the surface in the final phase of the decompression process. This situation was reported in the original SubCAS project (Shepherd 2018) and was also verified in the Biomarine project. To overcome this problem, three levels of bypasses were installed in the pressure line (before the chamber

entrance) to reduce interior flow. Basically, they work by throwing part of the system flow and, consequently, reducing the internal working pressure. These bypasses are made up of a ¼” pressure control valve and the other two are simple quick-connect ¼” valves. In the final part of the decompression process, when the main pressure control valve is no longer functional, the pressure is reduced by progressively opening the bypasses, starting with the control valve that offers greater precision and then the quick-connect ball valves. Depth values inside hyperbaric chamber were monitored throughout this process. Adjustments enabled the virtual depth inside the chamber to reach surface levels, even with a significant circulating flow.

A drop in electrical energy is a risk factor that must be considered because it will lead to rapid decompression of the hyperbaric chamber, which can be harmful or fatal to fish. A simple electrical protection system was also adopted in case of failure of the base AC power supply. For that, the Biomarine team used a small contactor switch with NC poles⁴ and connected it to the stationary battery system, which would supply the CC system in case of a power failure. Although successfully tested, no power failure occurred during the process.

A small ROV⁵ was implemented to support the operation. The equipment was very useful during the chamber’s recovery, to record part of the operation, and to monitor the diver’s condition.

The two operations were planned and executed at the northeast region of Brazil, at 13° 01’ 32.2” S and 38° 16’ 97.4” W (WGS 84). The location chosen was the coast of Bahia State, Salvador, because of the proximity of the continental shelf break and the availability of divers highly specialized in deep diving.

The first operation took place on 1/22/22. The dive follow-up was uneventful, with a maximum depth of 122 m for diver 1 and 138 m for diver 2. It lasted 4.5 hours and resulted in the capture of two French butterflyfish specimens.

Diver depth profile of dive performed on 1/22/22 (Diver László Mocsári).

Biomarine hyperbaric chamber in operation.

Specimens of Prognathodes guyanensis captured by Biomarine.

Fish were brought to surface inside the hyperbaric chamber by the dive support team, who retrieved the equipment at a depth of 30 m and brought it on board the support vessel, while the deep-sea divers remained in the water to decompress. The chamber was successfully connected to the pressure system and kept running. After the deep-sea divers returned to the boat, the team came back to shore. Despite careful planning and execution, temperature shock and high levels of ammonia resulted in the mortality of the two captured specimens.

In this work model, the entire team and the fish must wait for the dive team’s long decompression to return to shore, which increases the maintenance time of the fish on board, aggravating temperature issues if there is no thermal protection. Incidents linked to the temperature increase have been reported in the literature (Shepherd 2018). Although there was no success in keeping the fish alive in the first operation, Biomarine considered the result positive. Equipment and procedures were tested and demonstrated to be efficient. In addition, the decompression process successfully brought live specimens to the surface.

A second dive operation was performed on 2/26/2022.

Important improvements were adopted that focused on temperature maintenance using a thermal box⁶ with internal space to hold two hyperbaric chambers, including the hydraulic set, pump and line. The dive had a maximum depth of 123 m, with 10 min of descent, 21 min of effective bottom time and approximately 5 hr of decompression.

Two more specimens of French butterflyfish were captured at 110 m depth and brought to the surface in the hyperbaric chamber under a virtual pressure of 60 to 70 m. Temperature at the collection point was 21 C and at the sea surface was 28 C. Improving procedures, recovery logistics were modified so that the hyperbaric chamber could ascend quickly. The ROV was used to find divers

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in the 70-m range and affix the camera to the robotic arm. The assembly was then brought immediately to the surface. At this depth, the temperature is still cold and this would avoid subjecting the set to high surface temperature for an unnecessary time. The assembled hyperbaric chamber was attached to the ROV's arm and quickly brought on board without the support dive team. The set was then reconnected to the fully protected high-pressure system with cold water (21 C) inside the thermal box preserving fish's physiological condition.

The decompression process took 30 hr in total, always considering visual observations of the individuals, which on some occasions needed to be recompressed due to excessive buoyancy, especially in the final phase, the last 10 m. The need for recompression suggests the adoption of a specific decompression protocol, which considers longer downtimes during final stages of the process.

Finally, fishes were released from the hyperbaric chamber and kept at ambient pressure with water temperature close to original values (21 C), allowing a slight increase of 1 C per day over the three days after release to acclimate fish for transport. Maintenance at base was carried out with daily water exchange for fresh seawater kept under controlled temperature in an acclimatized room.

On the third day after release from the hyperbaric chamber, a period when the fish had undergone adaptation to ambient pressure, fish were placed in plastic bags containing seawater with a pure oxygen atmosphere and transported by air in a polystyrene box to Biomarine Ornamental Aquaculture (São Paulo/SP) facilities, and subjected to quarantine upon arrival. Currently, the specimens are healthy, accepting inert shrimp-based food.

Despite high costs and needs for improved equipment and procedures, the capture operations proved that it is possible to bring mesophotic fish to the surface with a high degree of safety, submitting them to proper decompression protocols without causing hyperbaric damage. Care to control temperature with specific equipment was as important as pressure control in the hyperbaric system, and it must be always prioritized; after all, mesophotic fish generally inhabit cold waters. At the capture site, temperatures varied from 28 to 30 C on the surface and from 18 to 20 C on the bottom (between 100 and 138 m). Technical improvements are essential to optimize locating and capturing specimens with gear that can provide passive fishing, diversification of specimens captured and improvements in diving procedures. Seeking greater operational efficiency, for future operations, the Biomarine team will consider a few changes, such as an increase in the number of bottom divers and fishing training in shallow waters.

Biomarine also intends to incorporate scientists specialized in mesophotic ichthyology who have training experience with rebreather use in deep dives, aiming to expand research contributions for these species and/or environments. Finally, the use of an ROV on deeper dives should allow increased substrate prospecting activities and deletion of locations with a biodiversity that is not in accord with operational objectives.

Benefits that knowledge about mesophotic fish can bring to environmental conservation are undeniable. Future results of captive breeding of these species can help to understand several biological mechanisms not yet elucidated by science. Biomarine intends to contribute very actively to the knowledge and conservation of mesophotic regions.

Notes

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- ¹ Shurflo 9325 043-101 12/24v
- ² Coel Z31 12/24v
- ³ Plastomatic RVDm In-line Pressure Relief Valve, PVC/EPDM Thd, Indelco Plastics Corporation, USA
- ⁴ WEG - CWCA0-22-00V26
- ⁵ FIFISH V6S, with 200-m cable
- ⁶ Coleman 120 Qt Blue nights

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